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Metal Complexes as Ligands. Tri-nuclear Alkali Metal Complexes with Nickel(II)- and Palladium(II)-bisdimethylglyoximates

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*Manuscript received 15 September 1984, revised 7 October 1986,
accepted 13 November 1986*

TO extend the studies on 'metal complexes as ligands', we have selected Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ bisdimethylglyoximates as the ligands. In this paper, an attempt has been made to synthesise and characterise hetero-trinuclear alkali metal complexes derived from alkali metal salts of 8-hydroxyquinoline, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol with Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ bisdimethylglyoximate denoted by Ni(DMGH)₂ and Pd(DMGH)₂, respectively.

Experimental

Synthesis of the adducts: A number of stable trinuclear adducts of alkali metal salts of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N) and 8-hydroxyquinoline

(8HQ) with Ni(DMGH)₂ and Pd(DMGH)₂ of the general formula [M_a(DMGH)₂(M_bL)₂], where M_a=Ni²⁺, Pd²⁺ and M_bL=Li, Na or K, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol or 8-hydroxyquinolines, were synthesised as the case may be. (i) The usual method of synthesis was to take Ni(DMGH)₂ or Pd(DMGH)₂ in absolute ethanol, and alkali metal salts were added to it in 1:2 molar ratio. The mixtures were refluxed on a hot-plate for 3-4 h with constant stirring, and the adducts were precipitated in hot condition. (ii) To a suspension of Ni(DMGH)₂ in absolute ethanol, one or two pellets of NaOH were added avoiding excess, and the whole mixture was stirred for 15 min. The red colour of Ni(DMGH)₂ changed to dark yellow and part of the product went into solution. The resulting disodium-bisdimethylglyoximates-Ni²⁺, Na₂[Ni(DMGH)₂] was treated with 1N2N/8HQ in absolute ethanol. The brownish red/pale green compounds that formed, were washed with ethanol and dried at 80°. The corresponding lithium and potassium complexes of Ni(DMGH)₂ and all the alkali metal adducts with Pd(DMGH)₂ were synthesised by the same method.

Analytical data, decomposition temperature and relevant ir bands are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

The colours of the adducts [M_a(DMGH)₂(M_bL)₂] are different from those of the complex ligands [M_a(DMGH)₂]. The higher decomposition temperatures of these adducts compared to those of M(DMGH)₂, showed the strong bonding, most likely through oxygen atoms of the 'complex ligand' to the alkali metals. These compounds are stable under anhydrous condition but decompose on

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE ADDUCTS M_a(DMGH)₂(M_bL)₂

Compd.*	Colour	Decomp. temp.	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)		
			N	Ni/Pd	Na/K
(Li1N2N) ₂ .X	Brown	285	12.3 (13.0)	9.4 (9.0)	-
(Na1N2N) ₂ .X	Brown	275	12.4 (11.7)	9.9 (8.6)	6.9 (6.4)
(K1N2N) ₂ .X	Brownish yellow	270	11.3 (11.8)	8.0 (8.1)	10.00 (11.01)
(Li8HQ) ₂ .X	Green	245	13.7 (14.2)	9.3 (9.8)	-
(Na8HQ) ₂ .X	Green	242	12.95 (13.50)	9.8 (9.3)	7.1 (7.4)
(K8HQ) ₂ .X	Green	230	11.9 (12.7)	9.20 (8.89)	10.8 (11.9)
(Li1N2N) ₂ .Y	Brown	290	12.7 (13.2)	15.8 (16.1)	-
(Na1N2N) ₂ .Y	Brownish grey	282	11.1 (11.5)	12.6 (13.2)	5.9 (6.3)
(K1N2N) ₂ .Y	Brownish black	280	12.0 (11.1)	13.2 (14.0)	9.6 (10.3)
(Li8HQ) ₂ .Y	Yellowish green	300	12.72 (13.20)	17.2 (16.6)	-
(Na8HQ) ₂ .Y	Greenish yellow	295	11.9 (12.5)	14.90 (15.86)	6.40 (6.88)
(K8HQ) ₂ .Y	Greenish yellow	288	11.1 (12.0)	14.0 (15.1)	10.8 (11.1)

*X = Ni(DMGH)₂, Y = Pd(DMGH)₂.

TABLE 2—IR BANDS OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	$\nu_{C=N}$ cm ⁻¹	ν_{N-O} cm ⁻¹
Ni(DMGH) ₂	1 576	1 241
Pd(DMGH) ₂	1 552	1 259
X (Li8HQ) ₂	1 586	1 230
X (Na8HQ) ₂	1 590	1 226
X (K8HQ) ₂	1 586	1 229
X (Li1N2N) ₂	1 586	1 214
X (Na1N2N) ₂	1 590	1 220
X (K1N2N) ₂	1 580	1 214
Y (Li1N2N) ₂	1 572	1 206
Y (K1N2N) ₂	1 560	1 212

*X—Ni(DMGH)₂, Y—Pd(DMGH)₂.

exposure to moisture. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Varian-Carry 14 spectrophotometer in nujol.

Results and Discussion

The C=N frequency of Ni(DMGH)₂ at 1 576 cm⁻¹ shifts to 1 580–1 590 cm⁻¹ in the alkali metal adducts; and the corresponding C=N of Pd(DMGH)₂ at 1 552 cm⁻¹ shows the upward trend in its adducts, observed at 1 560–1 572 cm⁻¹. Similar upward trend of C=N was observed for Pd/Ni(DMG)₂(BF₃)₂¹. The C=N stretching frequencies of alkali metal oxinates were observed at 1 550–1 540 cm⁻¹ (being part of the aromatic ring) and remain unchanged in the trinuclear adducts. The ν_{N-O} of Ni(DMGH)₂ at 1 241 cm⁻¹ shows a downward trend to 1 214–1 230 cm⁻¹ in the alkali metal adducts. For Pd(DMGH)₂, the ligand ν_{N-O} at 1 259 cm⁻¹ shifts to 1 206–1 212 cm⁻¹ in the alkali metal adducts. The observations of other workers²⁻⁵ on pyridine-N-oxide complexes, are similar. The ν_{N-O} of the 1N2N becomes a part of the ring in its alkali metal salt, and attains some double bond character as ν_{N-O} is observed at ~1 340 cm⁻¹. The C—O bond of alkali oxinates, being a part of the ring, attains a partial double bond character, and ν_{C-O} is observed at 1 520–1 500 cm⁻¹.

The electronic absorption band of medium intensity at 475 nm for Ni(DMGH)₂ and [Ni(DMG)₂(BF₃)₂], and at 510 nm for trinuclear alkali metal adducts derived from Ni(DMGH)₂ suggest that even in these trinuclear adducts, the central Ni^{II} retains its square-planar structure. All compounds of Ni^{II} are diamagnetic.

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Studies on Manganese(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Zinc(II) Complexes of Substituted Aryl Furyl β -Diketones

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Manuscript received 21 July 1986, revised 21 October 1986, accepted 13 November 1986

β -Diketones are well known for their biological activity¹. They are known to act as inhibitors against galvanic corrosion². Attempts have been made to evolve analytical methods for iron and steel by direct dissolution of metal in β -diketones³. The application of their metal complexes in various diverse fields such as column, thin layer and gas chromatography, solvent extraction, laser technique, nmr shift reagent and in polymer industry is however of comparatively recent origin⁴. Therefore, β -diketones have been extensively investigated for their complex forming ability⁵. The present study was undertaken with a view to investigate systematically the complex formation process between some transition metal ions and aryl furyl β -diketones.

- 1; R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = H
- 2; R₁ = CH₃, R = R₂ = H
- 3; R₂ = CH₃, R = R₁ = H

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The β -diketones, 1-(2-furyl)-3-(3',4'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)propane-1,3-dione (F-3',4'-DMPPD) (1), 1-(2-furyl)-3-(3',5'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)propane-1,3-dione (F-3',5'-DMPPD) (2) and 1-(2-furyl)-3-(3',6'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxyphenyl)propane-1,3-dione (F-3',6'-DMPPD) (3) were prepared and purified by the methods described earlier⁶. The metal ions were used in the form of their nitrates and were estimated by EDTA titrations⁷. Dioxane was purified by the standard method⁸.

The Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique involved the titrations of (i) 4×10^{-3} M HClO₄, (ii) 4×10^{-3} M HClO₄ + 2×10^{-3} M ligand, and (iii) 4×10^{-3} M HClO₄ + 2×10^{-3} M ligand + 4×10^{-4} M metal ion solutions against standard (1.833×10^{-2} N) carbonate-free NaOH solution.